

COGNITIVE WARFARE, AN URGENT FIX FOR THE ITALIAN DEFINITION

La cognitive warfare (CW) sta emergendo come un nuovo paradigma nei conflitti moderni, attirando crescente attenzione nel dibattito strategico internazionale. Questo studio analizza criticamente il concetto di CW così come definito nel documento "Cognitive Warfare – la competizione nella dimensione cognitiva" (2023) dello Stato Maggiore della Difesa italiano (SMD). Attraverso un'analisi qualitativa, concettuale e testuale basata sulle scienze strategiche, la ricerca mira a valutare la solidità concettuale dell'attuale definizione italiana di CW. I risultati evidenziano alcune carenze riguardo alla natura della CW, al suo rapporto con i principi storici della military deception e alla specificità degli obiettivi. Lo studio propone definizioni alternative e raccomandazioni concrete per affinare e consolidare il concetto italiano di cognitive warfare, contribuendo così al suo sviluppo teorico e operativo. Le implicazioni di questo studio possono allargare lo spazio di discussione in tema di cognitive warfare e favorire il lavoro concettuale dello SMD.

Parole chiave: cognitive warfare, strategia militare, dottrina italiana, analisi concettuale, military deception

Cognitive warfare (CW) is emerging as a new paradigm in modern conflicts, attracting increasing attention in international strategic debates. This study critically analyzes the concept of CW as defined in the 2023 document "Cognitive Warfare - Competition in the Cognitive Dimension" by the Italian Defence General Staff (IDGS). Through a qualitative and textual analysis based on strategic sciences, the research aims to evaluate the conceptual solidity of the current Italian definition of CW. The results highlight some deficiencies regarding the nature of CW, its relationship with historical principles of military deception, and the specificity of its objectives. The study proposes alternative definitions and concrete recommendations to refine and consolidate the Italian concept of cognitive warfare, thus contributing to its theoretical and operational development. Implications of this study can enlarge the field of discussion about cognitive warfare and support the IDGS in its conceptual work.

Keywords: cognitive warfare, military strategy, Italian doctrine, conceptual analysis, military deception

Introduction and literature review

With the publication of the document "Cognitive Warfare - Competition in the Cognitive Dimension," the IDGS has positioned itself at the forefront of efforts to provide a structured framework for the emerging concept of CW. Although the cognitive dimension is not a new aspect of war—as Clausewitz clearly states when he describes the ultimate aim of war as the subjugation of the enemy to our will¹⁰⁴—contemporary and future technologies, new domains, and the widespread connectivity available to much of the population could make the cognitive dimension more decisive than in the past. Traditional propaganda techniques can now leverage artificial intelligence and social networks to influence both adversary and friendly populations, while classic military deception can exploit space and cyber domains to amplify

¹⁰⁴CLAUSEWITZ, K., *Della Guerra*, Arnoldo Mondadori Editore, Roma 1970.

its effects. The literature on cognitive flaws is extensive, including well-known publications aimed at a general audience. Books such as *Thinking, Fast and Slow* by Daniel Kahneman (2011) and *Noise: A Flaw in Human Judgment* (2021) by Kahneman, Sibony, and Sunstein have brought the topics of cognitive biases and limitations to global attention, by a psychological perspective. Within NATO, work on cognitive issues related to warfare is still ongoing, and a shared definition of the concept is expected shortly. In recent years, the academic sphere has also dedicated itself to the study of this subject as evidenced by the seminal work of Du Cluzel (2021)¹⁰⁵, which defines cognitive warfare as "...the way of using knowledge for a conflicting purpose," and that of Claverie and Du Cluzel (2022)¹⁰⁶, which began to propose possible definitions and identify areas of development. Mahjoub Eshrat-abadi and Shakuri Moghani (2022)¹⁰⁷ highlight how there is often a risk of falling into fallacies that reduce CW exclusively to the psychological field, "cognitive operations," interference, compromise, military operations, or battlefield application. The debate has gradually been enriched by contributions such as the brilliant critical analysis of Deppe and Schaal (2024)¹⁰⁸, who have proposed their own formulation, attempting to bridge the gap between academic and institutional military definitions. In the same year, Drmotova and Kutej¹⁰⁹ identified three main segments of cognitive warfare: neuroscience, social sciences, and technology. Cambria and Curcio (2024)¹¹⁰ provided a brilliant definition of the cognitive dimension, both in general and operational terms. The Italian Defence has adopted a transitional definition, reported in the preface of the aforementioned document, which describes cognitive warfare as "... a multi-domain operation (or part thereof) that employs means, actions, and tools across the connections between classical domains (land, air, naval), space and cyber domains, the information environment, and the electromagnetic spectrum, influencing human behaviour and generating effects in the cognitive dimension, with the aim of gaining an advantage over the adversary." This approach, although certainly useful in establishing a starting point for discussion in the professional sphere, is exposed to potential misunderstandings and difficulties in the application phase.

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative and textual analysis approach rooted in strategic sciences to critically examine the concept of cognitive warfare (CW) as defined by the Italian Defence General Staff (IDGS). The research addresses two primary questions:

1. How can strategic science improve the Italian definition of cognitive warfare?
2. What practical options are available for the evolution of the current definition?

The analysis primarily focuses on the document "Cognitive Warfare - Competition in the Cognitive Dimension" published by the IDGS in 2023. The reason for this choice is that the named document is the only official and public position of the IDGS about CW. The methodology involves a critical examination of the components within the Italian CW definition, comparing it with existing strategic science concepts and military historical evidence. This approach allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the definition's strengths and weaknesses, grounded in established theoretical frameworks and historical precedents. The study proceeds through the detailed analysis of the IDGS definition, the comparison of these components with relevant concepts from strategic sciences and military history, the synthesis of findings to identify conceptual gaps and areas for improvement and the

¹⁰⁵ DU CLUZEL, F., *Cognitive Warfare*, NATO ACT Innovation Hub, 2021. Available at https://innovationhub-act.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20210113_CW-Final-v2-.pdf, visited on 13th november 2024.

¹⁰⁶ CLAVERIE, B. - DU CLUZEL, F. *The Cognitive Warfare Concept*, NATO ACT Innovation Hub, 2021. Available at https://innovationhub-act.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/CW-article-Claverie-du-Cluzel-final_0.pdf, visited on 13 november, 2024.

¹⁰⁷ MAHJOUB ESHRAT-ABADI, H. - SHAKURI MOGHANI, S., *Modern Cognitive Warfare: From the Application of Cognitive Science and Technology in the Battlefield to the Arena of Cognitive Warfare*, in «Journal of Human Resource Studies», 2022, Spring, Vol. 12, N. 2, pp. 156-180.

¹⁰⁸ DEPPE, C. - SCHAAL, G. S., *Cognitive warfare: a conceptual analysis of the NATO ACT cognitive warfare exploratory concept*, 2024. Available at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>, visited on 21 november 2024.

¹⁰⁹ DRMOTOVÁ, K. - LIBOR, K. *Cognitive Warfare as a New Dimension of Security. A Fictional Concept or a Real Silent Threat?*, in *Vojenskè Rozhledy (Czech Military Review)*, 2024, available at <https://vojenskerozhledy.cz/en/>, visited on 21 november 2024.

¹¹⁰ CAMBRIA, A. - CURCIO, M. *A definition of cognitive dimension and its exploitation in the military affairs*, in «Strategic Leadership Journal», 2024, Vol. III.

formulation of alternative definitions that address the identified shortcomings.

Findings

The findings of the study highlight three key deficiencies in the Italian Defence General Staff's (IDGS) definition of cognitive warfare (CW). Firstly, the current characterization of CW as merely an "operation" is seen as inadequate, failing to encompass its broader strategic implications and transformative potential. Secondly, the definition does not clearly differentiate between cognitive effects and behavioural outcomes, a critical oversight that undermines the practical application and evaluation of CW strategies. Lastly, the stated objective of gaining an advantage over adversaries is too generic because does not provide any specific characterization of the possible competitive advantage provided by CW. These findings underscore the necessity for a revised definition by the IDGS.

Discussion

Only an "operation"?

The definition provided by the IDGS states that cognitive warfare is an operation. Using NATO's definition of operation, which is "a sequence of coordinated actions with a defined purpose"¹¹¹, what is called warfare in the name is then defined differently. This does not represent a problem so much for the semantic difference as for the breadth and ambition of CW itself. Indeed, a coordinated sequence of actions presupposes both an available doctrine that allows practical application, a characteristic currently not applicable in the field of CW. If the aspiration is to create a new way of war, the term operations is far too limited. According to Echevarria, a way of war "...implies thinking about conflict holistically, from prewar condition-setting to the final accomplishment of one's strategic objectives"¹¹². Referring to Echevarria¹¹³, it is also highlighted how relevant it is to be aware of a structural difference between what could be a *way of war* and a *way of battle*. Echevarria, in fact, although in a different context, highlights how the current American way of war is more a way of battle. Echevarria's critique, writing this article in 2004, points to the fact that American military culture is focused on purely technical military aspects and does not effectively connect success in war with the achievement of political objectives. For our purposes, however, this differentiation can be particularly useful in helping and guiding us in reasoning about CW and its future evolution. The American strategist's reasoning suggests a question that CW theory should answer, namely whether it should be considered (or if one wants to develop it as) a way to win the war or also a solution to "win the peace". A definition of CW according to this canon would, therefore, allow emphasizing its comprehensive approach, assuming a high level of ambition even without already having a fully available doctrine.

Another opportunity is to define CW as a theory of war, as it adequately falls within being a "... epistemology relating to the phenomenon of war, and all its related aspects, that seeks to understand it and its links to wider conflict; and provide a framework for the valid creation and dissemination of knowledge concerning war and warfare"¹¹⁴. Considering CW as a theory of war would emphasize the multi-domain character and transversality to the instruments of national power. In this case, the level of ambition would be maximum, aiming to develop a holistic approach in confronting war itself. Moreover, we should consider that Clausewitz, in "On war", explicitly states that theory should not aim to dictate actions through rigid rules but should instead provide tools for understanding war's nature and dynamics. He writes, "Theory should be study, not doctrine. This point of view makes theory possible and eliminates its conflict with reality"¹¹⁵. For Clausewitz, another key requirement for a theory of war is the importance of grounding theory in historical experience. He writes, "The knowledge which is basic to the art of war is empirical"¹¹⁶ emphasizing that historical examples provide clarity and proof in understanding war's nature. However, he cautions against misusing history by drawing simplistic analogies or applying outdated lessons without considering contemporary

¹¹¹ NATOTerm database, visited on 20 november 2024.

¹¹² ECHEVARRIA, A. J., *Toward an American Way of War*, USAWC Press, 01 march 2004.

¹¹³ Ibid.

¹¹⁴ BOSIO, N. J. *Understanding war's theory: what military theory is, where it fits, and who influence it?*, Australian Army Occasional paper, april 2018.

¹¹⁵ CLAUSEWITZ, K., op. cit.

¹¹⁶ Ibid.

contexts.

Another way to address this issue is to consider CW a strategic theory. Colin Gray believes that a strategic theory "...educates the mind by providing intellectual organization, defining terms, suggesting connections among apparently disparate matters, and offering speculative consequentialist postulates"¹¹⁷. Adopting such an approach would then aspire to provide a solid corpus of ends, ways, and means applicable to the contemporary context, while unleashing the exciting potential of producing cognitive strategies.

If, on the contrary, one aspired to a more limited definition, it might prove opportune to orient oneself towards the observation of the state of the art here and now, using *ad hoc* formulations that capture only and exclusively what is reasonably and predictably possible to insert in this field. Although less appealing, the use of descriptions such as "integrated employment of means and methods...", instead of the term operation, would return a realistic picture of what exists and could reasonably exist, while still leaving room for the possibility of real employment of some of these means and methods, even in the face of a doctrine that is not yet structured. This range of formulations would certainly be less ambitious but would probably respond to more practical needs.

Cognitive Warfare and Multidomain approach

The IDGS definition states clearly that CW is multidomain. This represents a coherent and logical evolution from several perspectives. First, ongoing western doctrines defines themselves as "multidomain". While it remains debatable whether this is an actual characteristic or merely an aspirational end state, aligning CW with current doctrinal frameworks ensures consistency. Second, military history—particularly in the context of deception—provides valuable insights. A key lesson from the practice of deception is that a ruse directed at an enemy through only one source or channel is often destined to fail, as demonstrated by the works of Barton Whaley¹¹⁸ about the historical evidence of success and failure in military deception. We can reasonably argue that historical evidence supports the aspiration for CW to be multidomain by design, even if it is not an inherently necessary feature.

The "friendly side of Cognitive Warfare"

The current Italian definition of CW primarily emphasizes its application against adversaries. However, this definition does not explicitly address the role of CW in enhancing the cognitive capabilities of friendly forces, even though such an implication can be inferred from the broader context of the document. The document highlights the importance of leveraging emerging technologies and integrating cognitive strategies across various domains, suggesting that CW is not solely about degrading adversary cognition but also about enhancing one's own. For instance, references to "cognitive enhancement" and the integration of interdisciplinary resources indicate potential applications for improving decision-making, situational awareness, and operational effectiveness within friendly forces. Nevertheless, these aspects remain implicit and are not clearly articulated as part of CW's definition. This omission risks underrepresenting a critical dimension of CW—its potential to strengthen friendly capabilities in addition to countering threats. To fully capture the dual nature of CW, it would be beneficial for the Italian definition to explicitly include its application to the friendly side.

"What do you want the enemy to do?"

A subsequent part of the CW definition by IDGS states "... influencing human behaviour and generating effects in the cognitive dimension...", appropriately highlighting the characteristic elements of this new methodology of confrontation and conflict. The main issue with this part of the definition lies in the fact that the pursuit and achievement of cognitive effects is never sufficient to accomplish anything. There is a substantial difference between possible cognitive effects and actual behaviours. This difference is excellently illustrated by addressing the foundations of military deception and using some solid historical evidence like the one of Col. Dudley Clarke during the II world war. In 1941, Col. Dudley Clarke had already been in

¹¹⁷ GRAY, C. S. *Modern strategy*, Oxford University Press, Oxford 1999, p. 36.

¹¹⁸ WHALEY, B., *Practice to deceive – learning curves of military deception planners*, Naval Institute Press, Annapolis 2016 e WHALEY, B., *Tournabout and Deception: crafting the double-cross and the theory of out*, Naval Institute Press, Annapolis 2016.

command of the so-called "A" Force for a year, which was the group of planners based in Cairo responsible for English deception plans for Gen. Archibald Wavell, as part of British operations in Africa. That year, Clarke prepared the deception plan against Italian forces in Ethiopia and found himself addressing the very issue of cognitive effects and expected behaviours. Even though the deception was well executed, the Italians did exactly the opposite of what was expected of them. We can read from his own word the faced challenge from his memoirs: "In the first Deception Plan I ever tackled I learned a lesson of inestimable value. The scene was Abyssinia.... Gen. Wavell wanted the Italians to think he was about to attack them from the south in order to draw of forces from those opposing him on the northern flank. The Deception went well enough-but the result was just the opposite of what Wavell wanted. The Italians drew back in the South, and sent what they could spare from there to the North, which was of course the true British objective. After that it became a creed in "A" Force to ask a General – What do you want the enemy do to? – and never – What do you want him to think?"¹¹⁹. Clarke encountered the same type of conceptual difficulty that transpires from the current definition of CW, namely failing to unequivocally clarify that the actual goal is a behaviour experienced by a person or group of people and not just a perception or thought. More recently in 2021, Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) purportedly and successfully deceived Hamas fighters using mass media and social networks. In this case the connection between cognitive effect and actual behaviours worked quite effectively. As described in the words of a New York Times article "The Israeli military abruptly announced after midnight on Friday that its ground forces had begun - attacking in the Gaza Strip - saying it on Twitter, in text messages to journalists, and in on-the-record confirmations by an English-speaking army spokesman. Several international news organizations, including The New York Times, immediately alerted readers worldwide that a Gaza incursion or invasion was underway, a major escalation of Israeli-Palestinian hostilities. Within hours, those reports were all corrected: No invasion had taken place. Rather, ground troops had opened fire at targets in Gaza from inside Israeli territory, while fighters and drones were continuing to attack from the air. A top military spokesman took responsibility, blaming the fog of war. But by Friday evening, several leading Israeli news outlets were reporting that the incorrect announcement was no accident but had actually been part of an elaborate deception. The intent, the media reports said, was to dupe Hamas fighters into thinking that an invasion had begun and to respond in ways that would expose far greater numbers of them to what was being called a devastatingly lethal Israeli attack."¹²⁰. This example shows clearly that the desired strategic or tactical effect needs to be something performed in practical ways.

This "cognitive-behaviours link" remains valid even when it comes to influencing groups of people, political and social leaders, and not just military decision-makers. One always seeks a desired behaviour (even in a negative direction), be it a vote, a *like*, or an operational decision. Consequently, stating that CW performs its function by "influencing behaviour and generating cognitive effects"¹²¹ dangerously places on the same level two effects that are one the consequence of the other. This part of the definition could be corrected by explicating the correct logical sequence of the two parts or by eliciting the part of cognitive effects, safeguarding the purpose that describes the achievement of desirable behavioural effects.

A solution looking for a problem

We thus arrive at the final part of the definition of CW, namely the specification of its purpose. The IDGS writes that CW has "...the objective of gaining an advantage over the adversary."¹²² This purpose, drafted in such generic terms, corresponds to the immediate purpose of any competitive activity. The fundamental problem is of a logical nature, as the parties involved in a competitive relationship will necessarily seek an advantage over the adversary. However, the absence of a shared, clear, and qualifying purpose is a symptom and not the problem. CW's potential is hindered by the diverse range of activities and tools associated with it, making it objectively difficult to identify a characterizing purpose. This ensemble, consisting mainly of diversified resources and technologies, struggles to solve a

¹¹⁹ WHALEY, B., *Practice to deceive – learning curves of military deception planners*, Naval Institute Press, Annapolis 2016, p. 33.

¹²⁰ HALBFINGER, D., *A press corps deceived, and the Gaza invasion that wasn't*, New York Times, 14/05/2021, visited on 20/02/2025, <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/05/14/world/middleeast/israel-gaza-disinformation.html>

¹²¹ SMD, *cognitive warfare*, op. cit.

¹²² Ibid.

problem more specific than a generic advantage over the adversary. The difficulty is profound because, even if one were to try to introduce a more recognizable purpose, such as the modification of behaviours, one would quickly fall back into the realm of multi-domain and technologically advanced deception, which would still leave out many elements that can currently fall under CW, such as the pharmacological enhancement of cognitive performance. The problem of purpose coincides with the problem of delimiting the field of action, and they can hardly be separated from each other. In this field, C. J. Wylie's interpretation of the main descriptive pattern of war can help us: "...as far as the aggressor is concerned, the pattern of war consists of his attempts to establish and maintain, primarily by military means, a measure of control over the conservator sufficient to force the conservator to conform to whatever may be the aggressor's terms."¹²³. Understanding war as an attempt to establish a certain degree of control over the adversary perfectly aligns with the emerging concept of CW, facilitating the linkage of such variety of tools and techniques with a political objective.

Limitations

This study has several limitations, mainly the lack of quantitative analysis and the probable cognitive biases of the qualitative approach. Moreover, approaching the field by the perspective of strategic sciences and military history leaves several points of view not covered. It's also important to note that while the study proposes alternative definitions based on identified flaws, there may be other potential formulations of cognitive warfare that have not been considered. The field's complexity and interdisciplinary nature suggest that further definitions could be derived from different analytical approaches or emerging research in related domains.

Way ahead for the Cognitive Warfare's definition and practical implications

In conclusion, an in-depth analysis of the Italian definition of CW has revealed several conceptual gaps that warrant careful consideration. Firstly, the characterization of CW as a mere "operation" proves inadequate in capturing its true essence and transformative potential. This limited conceptualization risks underestimating the scope and impact of CW, opening an opportunity for a discussion aimed at elevating it to the status of a "way of war" or even a "theory of war". Such a reformulation would allow for the recognition of the holistic and pervasive nature of CW, which transcends the traditional boundaries of military operations. A second critical aspect emerges from the failure to distinguish between cognitive and behavioural effects in the current definition. This omission not only neglects a fundamental principle well-rooted in the practice of military deception but also risks diverting attention from the concrete and measurable objectives of CW. It is essential to recognize that, while cognitive alterations are a crucial means, the true purpose of CW lies in modifying the observable behaviours of our audience or person of interest. This clarification is not merely semantic but has profound implications for planning and evaluating the effectiveness of CW operations. Furthermore, the generality of the stated objective - "to gain an advantage over the adversary" - proves insufficient in capturing the specificity and innovative potential of CW. This vague formulation could apply to any form of conflict or competition, failing to highlight what makes CW unique and potentially revolutionary. Ultimately, given the experimental momentum undertaken by the IDGS in formulating an initial definition of CW, a revision is desirable to create a robust conceptual framework that recognizes CW as an emerging paradigm in the conduct of warfare, capable of integrating cognitive, behavioural, and technological elements into a coherent, albeit transitory and evolving, body of knowledge. The following recommended definitions, based on the level of ambition and comprehensiveness to which one might aspire, provide viable options for the progression of the Italian definition of CW by the Italian Defence:

- Cognitive warfare is a theory of war that considers it essential that the domain of human cognition be enhanced in the friendly part and degraded in the hostile one in order to obtain a certain degree of control over the adversary and, consequently, the desired political objectives (Italian: *la cognitive warfare è una teoria della guerra che ritiene essenziale che l'ambito della cognizione umana sia potenziato nella parte amica e*

¹²³ WYLIE, J. C. *Military strategy: a general theory of power control*, Naval Institute Press, Annapolis 2014.

degradato in quella ostile al fine di ottenere un certo grado di controllo sull'avversario e, conseguentemente, gli obiettivi politici desiderati).

- Cognitive warfare is a method of warfare that, through the use of interdisciplinary resources and a multi-domain approach, aims to achieve strategic, operational, and tactical objectives, thanks to the achievement of cognitive enhancement of one's own forces and the simultaneous cognitive degradation of those of the adversary (Italian: la *cognitive warfare* è un metodo di guerra che, attraverso l'impiego di risorse interdisciplinari e approccio multidominio, mira ad ottenere obiettivi strategici, operativi e tattici, grazie al potenziamento cognitivo delle proprie forze e al contemporaneo degradamento cognitivo di quelle avversarie).
- Cognitive warfare is the integrated employment of interdisciplinary resources and a multi-domain approach, characterized by the cognitive enhancement of one's own forces and the simultaneous cognitive degradation of those of the adversary in order to contribute to the success of an operation or mission (Italian: la *cognitive warfare* è l'impiego integrato di risorse interdisciplinari e approccio multidominio, caratterizzato dal potenziamento cognitivo delle proprie forze e dal contemporaneo degradamento cognitivo di quelle avversarie al fine di contribuire al successo di un'operazione o missione).

Further scientific research could provide alternative ways to elaborate the definitions, different frameworks and processes for the analysis, new methods to integrate cognitive warfare ways and means as well as comparative approaches could benefit a better understanding of the cognitive warfare.

By a practical perspective, IDGS could take steps to foster a CW culture within the Armed Forces. The more ambitious the chosen definition of CW, the greater the effort required to enhance CW practices, training, and education. The cultural shift needed could be significant and must begin as early as the education phase following personnel recruitment. The most affected groups are likely to be Officers and Non-Commissioned Officers, along with their respective education and training pathways. Specifically, the Armed Forces should:

- introduce basic deception principles and techniques during the early stages of education in military academies;
- by default, incorporate deception planning into training and exercises;
- utilize wargaming as a tool for cognitive warfare experimentation and training;
- offer more advanced cognitive warfare theory (and potentially practical applications) during the Joint Staff Course (Istituto Superiore di Stato Maggiore Interforze, ISSMI).